

CORRELATIONS BETWEEN OBJECTIVE PROSTATE ENLARGEMENT AND PATIENTS' SUBJECTIVE PERCEPTION OF SYMPTOMS

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ABSTRACT

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) or adenoma is most often diagnosed in men over 40. Statistics show that the condition affects almost half of urologists' patients under 50. In patients over 70, the incidence is even higher – more than 80–85%. These World Health Organization statistics indicate a high prevalence of the disease among the global male population.

Introduction. The prevalence of LUTS associated with BPH ranges from 20% to 40% among men over 50 years of age in various populations worldwide.

Enlarged prostate volume can lead to urethral obstruction, obstructed urine flow, and, consequently, to the progression of lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS). Ultrasound is the standard method for quantifying prostate volume, and the IPSS questionnaire is used for a structured assessment of LUTS severity.

Despite the widespread use of these tools, debate continues in the literature regarding the degree of correlation between objective prostate enlargement and patients' subjective perception of symptoms. Clarifying this relationship is important for individual prognosis of the disease course and the selection of optimal treatment strategies.

Purpose of the study. To determine the degree of correlation between objective increase in prostate volume and subjective perception of symptoms by patients and the severity of lower urinary tract symptoms according to the IPSS scale in patients with BPH.

Material and research methods. A prospective observational study was conducted at a multidisciplinary clinic in Fergana.

The study included 220 men aged 50–80 years, with an average age of 66.5 ± 8.7 years, diagnosed with benign prostatic hyperplasia and LUTS.

The following methods were used: ultrasound, IPSS (International Prostate Symptom Score), and statistical analysis. Analysis was performed using SPSS v.23.

Research results and their discussion. The study revealed that the average prostate volume measured by ultrasound was $48.3 \pm 15.6 \text{ cm}^3$. The average IPSS score was 18.2 ± 6.4 . Patients were also distributed across prostate volume and IPSS categories. The distribution showed that patients with a prostate volume $\geq 50 \text{ cm}^3$ had significantly higher IPSS scores compared to patients with smaller volumes ($p < 0.01$). Correlation analysis revealed a moderately strong positive association between prostate volume and LUTS severity.

Patients with smaller prostate volumes ($<30 \text{ cm}^3$) had mild to moderate symptoms on average, while those with volumes $\geq 50 \text{ cm}^3$ had significant LUTS according to the IPSS. This means that with increasing hyperplastic tissue, the likelihood of urethral obstruction and impaired voiding dynamics increases.

However, the relationship between prostate volume and LUTS is not absolute—not all patients with large prostates experience severe symptoms, which may be due to factors such as bladder neck tone, detrusor function, and comorbidities.

Comparison of objective ultrasound data and subjective IPSS assessments allows the physician to obtain a more complete picture of the disease and choose the optimal treatment strategy: from drug therapy to surgical intervention.

Conclusions. There is a statistically significant positive correlation between prostate volume and the severity of lower urinary tract symptoms ($r = 0.62$, $p < 0.001$). Patients with prostate volume $\geq 50 \text{ cm}^3$ have higher IPSS scores, indicating significant LUTS. The results confirm the clinical value of using ultrasound and the IPSS simultaneously to assess the severity and dynamics of BPH.

References:

1. Лапшихина Е.А., Муслов С.А. ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ БОЛЬНЫХ РАКОМ ПРЕДСТАТЕЛЬНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ И ПСИХОМЕТРИЧЕСКИЕ СВОЙСТВА ОПРОСНИКА EORTC QLQ-PR25 // Научное обозрение. Медицинские науки. 2021. № 4. С. 16-31; URL: <https://science-medicine.ru/ru/article/view?id=1200> (дата обращения: 21.02.2026). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17513/srms.1200>
2. Polackwich AS, Shoskes DA. Chronic prostatitis/chronic pelvic pain syndrome: a review of evaluation and therapy. *Prostate Cancer Prostatic Dis.* 2016;19(2):132-138. DOI: 10.1038/pcan.2016.8
3. Zhang R, Sutcliffe S, Giovannucci E, Willett WC, Platz EA, Rosner BA, Dimitrakoff JD, Wu K. Lifestyle and Risk of Chronic Prostatitis/Chronic Pelvic Pain Syndrome in a Cohort of United States Male Health Professionals. *J Urol.* 2015;194(5):1295-1300. DOI: 10.1016/j.juro.2015.05.100
4. Коган М.И. Морфологические доказательства ишемической природы фиброза при синдроме хронической тазовой боли. Эффективная фармакотерапия. 2019;15(1):50-51. Kogan M.I. Morfologicheskie dokazatel'stva ishemicheskoy prirody fibroza pri sindrome hronicheskoy tazovoj boli. *Effektivnaya farmakoterapiya.* 2019;15(1):50-51. (In Russian). eLIBRARY ID: 37113532; EDN: SWWKMS